

Assessment of Health Impacts of Mineral-Rich Groundwater and Evaluation of Treatment Options for Safe Drinking Water for coastal village

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Abstract: Gujarat has a coastline of about 1,600 km, and based on the 2011 Census, it has the longest coastline in India, comprising 15 coastal districts with a population of more than 10 lakh people. In many coastal villages of Gujarat, groundwater is the primary source of drinking water; however, it often contains excessive concentrations of dissolved minerals such as total dissolved solids (TDS), chlorides, fluorides, hardness, and minerals such as bauxite and calcite. Nana Ashota village in Jamnagar District faces similar challenges, where long-term consumption of mineral-rich groundwater has raised serious concerns regarding public health. This study assesses the quality of groundwater in Nana Ashota village and evaluates the associated health impacts on the local population. Water samples were collected from different wells used by villagers for drinking and domestic purposes and were analyzed for key physico-chemical parameters. The results were compared with standard drinking water quality guidelines. A health survey was also conducted to identify the prevalence of water-related health problems such as skin diseases, eye problems, kidney stones, digestive issues, and hair fall. The results indicate that several water quality parameters exceed permissible limits, which may contribute to gastrointestinal disorders, dental, skeletal issues, and eye-related problems such as cataracts. Based on these findings, suitable water treatment methods are suggested to remove excess minerals and to provide safe drinking water. The study proposes techno-economically feasible and sustainable treatment solutions to improve drinking water quality and public health in the coastal village of Nana Ashota.

Key words: TDS, Hardness, drinking water standards, health problems, water treatment

Introduction

The demand for potable water, currently estimated at 710 bcm, is expected to increase to nearly 1,150 bcm by 2050, thus exceeding the supply. Though India currently has adequate water resources, an analysis of the water availability on a per capita basis indicates that India is moving towards a classification of 'water stressed', i.e., less than 1,700 m³ /person/ year. Also, India has lower average per capita water availability than other countries this can show in Fig1.0 of world water availability colour chart. This chart India is shown in yellow colour means water stress country. This chart can also explain that more than half of the world countries are under water scare.

Fig.1. world water availability

The heterogeneity in water availability across the country, given the wide variation in rainfall, only exacerbates the situation. This shown that 80% of water is received in monsoon season only & that too some time in only 10 to 15 days.

Also, the present infrastructure in the country is limited, in terms of long-distance transmission lines or canal networks, in its ability to carry water from regions with water surplus to regions with water scarcity. Thus, in arid regions in India, women and children wake up early to travel long distances to collect water. The situation in urban India is also quite dismal most of the cities receive very limited water.

All these have led to increasing dependence on groundwater. The result has been a steady depletion in the groundwater levels in many parts of the country. In Punjab, for example, while groundwater has helped the agricultural sector flourish, there are reports of groundwater being overdrawn in several blocks of the state. This has led to an alarming deterioration in the quality of water, which then leads to diseases such as fluorosis and cancer. Similar cases of overdrawn groundwater are prevalent in water-starved states like

Gujarat and Rajasthan. So, what are the possible solutions to this impending water crisis?

Gujarat is a water stressed state, with its per capita availability of fresh water at 1137 m³ (less than 1700 m³ per year). Several region of the state even suffer from chronic water shortages. This shortage is reflected in the shortage of potable water in many parts of the state, particularly in North Gujarat, Saurashtra and Kutch. Though efforts have been made to ensure adequate water supply to all, somehow these efforts have not been very successful. There is therefore a need to take a fresh look at the problem and at the efforts in Order to understand the problem better and to reorient the efforts. This thesis is based on this water problem regarding water in the coastal area of Gujarat specially in Saurashtra and Kutch this also provide them to new source of water in unsafe water in the coastal zone.

Last 28 years out of the 70 years Saurashtra has suffered scare city and declared drought affected zone. That's why this area is shown in national drought zone map published by Govt of India. Lack of less source of water Saurashtra and Kutch regions in Gujarat has been more than 70% area depending on ground water for drinking and irrigation purpose. presently state government has been starting many projects to increasing ground water table and to construct the check dams this gives result to increase ground water more than 10 meter in last five years. some of this area have sufficient ground water but not more used because of ground minerals, sea water intrusion polluted water and its makes unsafe water. Reasons for unsafe water is due to major content of chloride, hardness of carbonation, more content of fluoride, magnesium and potassium, calcite, TDS is more than 4000 mg/l and it is not suitable for drinking water. Saurashtra has long sea shore and rain falls has not sufficient in amount or not even in time period since last 20 year so sea water intrusion inside the land in the several kilometers and to lead polluting fresh water. This can increase TDS and result of this makes unsafe water for drinking purpose. for unsafe water, it is due to major content of chloride, hardness of carbonation, more content of fluoride, magnesium and potassium, calcite, TDS is more than 6000 mg/l and it is not suitable for drinking water.

Selection of village:

Largest Taluka in Jamnagar District and vary famous for oil refinery. Nana Ashota village is located in khambhalia Taluka. It is 25 km distance from main city khambhalia. Nana Ashota village is at 22.41°N 69.00°E It has an average elevation of 7 metres (22 feet) from mean sea level. Criteria for selection of village is minimum population nearby 1000, located near costal base, scare in most of the year, near the calcite and box site mines, from the list of GWWSB and other Govt Agencies more than thirty villages of khambhalia and kalyanpure Taluka in Jamnagar District has covered under these criteria. Nana Ashota and Mota Ashota village is twin villages and just in 5 km distance between them and both are 35 km from the khambhalia city. Nana Ashota is less population and just 10 km from sea shore, many mines near this village. This village used only ground water and all wells of gram panchayat have unsafe declared by govt. agencies. Narmada water pipe line is passing from 20 km from the Village and extended up to this village will be in proposed work.

Soil Texture and classification (Jamnagar land Texture)

- Basalt up to 300-meter depth in East to West
- Miliolite lime stone and calcareous sand stone in north part up to 20 to 30 meters
- Coarse and grained plates in south of Jamnagar

Ground Water Condition in study area

The water table comparison chart shown in fig.2. This comparison chart is between different months and different well’s water table in feet. This chart has confirmed that during January to June six month water table at below 28 ft while June to December next six months have averagely above 28 ft means ground water table has fluctuation between highest water table 25 feet to 31 feet.

Table.1. Ground Water Depth

Period	Water Level Condition	Series (Well No. 1)	Series II (Well No. 2)	Series III (Well No. 3)	Series IV (Well No. 4)
January to June	Water level is below 28 ft from the top of the well	Below 28 ft	Below 28 ft	Below 28 ft	Below 28 ft
June to December	Water level is above 28 ft from the top of the well	Above 28 ft	Above 28 ft	Above 28 ft	Above 28 ft

Fig. 2. water table comparison chart

Table.2. Rainfall Data collection in last 5 year

Year	Jan	Feb.	Mar	April	May	June	July	Aug.	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
2007	00	43	00	00	00	132	50	34	162.7	00	0.4	00
2008	0.5	0.7	0.1	00	00	130.2	68	22	192.6	.8	0.5	2.5
2009	00	0.0	0.0	00	00	128.4	55	212	125	4.4	0.2	00
2010	0.3	0.0	0.0	00	00	112.2	35	207	237.1	3	62	00
2011	00	0.4	0.0	00	00	242	0.73	6	352.4	0.0	0.1	00
2012	0.3	0.5	0.0	00	00	80	20	8	5	0.0	0.1	00

Note: (1) The District Rainfall(mm.) (R/F) shown below are the arithmetic averages of Rainfall of Stations under the District.

- (2) % Dep. are the Departures of rainfall from the long period averages of rainfall for the district.
- (3) Blank Spaces show non-availability of Data.
- (4) All data in mm
- (5) Source form IMD

Main source of water in this village is as follow

1. Surface water (check Dam)
2. Ground water
3. Narmada water through pipe line
4. Tanker water supply

Quantity details for diff. month of different well

There are four Gram Panchayat wells and every month wise ground water level has received from Gram panchayat office which help to find more suitable well for resources to supplying water to the village throughout the year, following data table from January to December of ground water level. From Central Ground Water Department is given data about the coefficient of permeability of soil K is 5×10^{-2} to 5×10^{-3} and water transmissible T is around 10000 litre /day/meter to 100000 litre/day/meter.

Table. 3. Water table level in different wells is given below

Month	Well 1 (water in ft)	Well2 (water in ft)	Well3 (water in ft)	Well4 (water in ft)
January	28	28.2	28.1	28
February	28.6	28	28.3	28.4
March	30	30.1	29.8	31
April	30.2	30.3	30.2	30.4
May	30.4	30.3	30.6	30.7
June	28	28.1	28	28.1
July	27	26.8	26.9	26.6
August	26	26.5	26.4	26.5
Sep	27.1	27.3	27.2	27.3
Oct	27.5	27.6	27.8	27.8
Nov	28	28.1	28.2	28.3
Dec	28.2	28.5	28.5	28.4

Fig.3. water quality standards in Different wells Dissolved solid and Chloride in wells

Fig.4. water quality standards in Different wells Calcium content and TDS in wells

Month wise Water table in Different wells: Fig. 2.21 showed January month water table level of different wells from well top. This can understand that in this month well 1 and well 3 have more quantity of water. While Fig .2.22 is shown well 1 & 3 have more water tables in April. Fig. 2.23 & 2.24 is shown July and Oct. It is clear that well 4 and well 1 have more water tables respectively. Ultimately from chart it is clear that well 1 has more quantity of water in throughout year.

Table.4. Water Quality table for village wells

CHARACTERISTIC	Desirable	Permissible	Well 1	Well2	Well3	Well4
COLOUR HAZEN UNITS	5	25	Colerless	Colerless	Colerless	Colerless
ODOUS	U. O	U. O	U. O	U. O	U. O	U. O
TURBIDITY NTU	5	10	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
DISSOLVED SOLIDS (mg/l)	500	2000	7024	6880	5900	8200
PH	6.5 to 8.5	----	6.68	7.2	7.1	6.9
TOTAL HARDNESS (as CaCo3) mg/l	300	600	3144	3200	4050	4000
CALCIUM (as Ca) mg/l	75	200	661	665	580	700
MAGNESSIUM (as Mg) mg/l	30	100	373	363	345	380
CHLORIDES (as Cl) mg/l	250	1000	2148	2400	2245	2346
SULPHATES (as SO4) mg/l	200	400	524	498	560	552
NITRATES (as NO3) mg/l	45	---	112.96	108	122	120.23
FLORIDES (as F) mg/l	1.0	1.5	.18	.12	.29	.15
ALKALINITY (as CaCO3) mg/l	200	600	160	140	180	190

Note: tested and certified by gwssb lab at Jamnagar

Diseases Due to Water in the village

In most of following type of disease is shown in this area especially for water born disease

- Malaria
- Diphtheria
- Yellow fever
- Skin disease
- Diphtheria
- Jaundice
- Stone in kidney
- Eye disease
- Fluorosis
- Gastric problem

Table.5. Local hospital data for every month wise

Month (year 2018)	No of people register for water bone disease
January	52
February	39
March	83
April	86
May	22

Fig.4. Water quality table for village wells:

Different Techno Economical methods:

So many different methods are available to solve this problem by providing proper treatment plant and it is based on technical and economical. Criteria for selection of methods are Energy consumption, technical skill, Instrument availability, Local material available, Economic way, Less Maintenance, more Efficiency are used as prime factor

These methods are

1. Reverse Osmosis Plant method
2. Thermal Distillation Process
3. Narmada Pipe line water Supply
4. Water Harvesting System

RO Plant: The phenomenon of osmosis occurs when pure water flows from a dilute Saline solution through a membrane into a higher concentrated saline solution. Membrane is placed between two compartments. “Semi-permeable” means that the membrane is permeable to some species, and not permeable to others.

Summary:

Capacity: 100000 liter per day
 Installation cost: Rs 20, 75,000 /-
 Main. cost: Rs 7, 56,000/- per Annum

Land required: 50 sqmt RCC const.
 Total men power: 2 No
 Electric connection: 7 HP III phase

Description	RO Plant
Cost per 1000 liter	Rs 30
Maintenance	YES
Quality of output water	GOOD
Energy Requirement	YES
Investment per 100000 liter/day	2075000
Area req.	50 sqmt

Conclusion & Recommendation:

- RO plant is one of the most suitable options for this region from a cost perspective; however, its maintenance is relatively expensive and labour-intensive.
- RO plants are mainly suitable for small communities and provide excellent results in reducing TDS, hardness, and other impurities. With some modifications or additional treatment processes, even better results can be achieved for groundwater purification.
- This system provides independence in controlling water purification, flexibility in the quantity of water used, and the ability to modify the treatment process according to local requirements.
- The operating cost mainly depends on the energy consumed by the pump. However, using solar panels for energy generation is a good option to reduce the overall operating cost of the RO plant.
- This method is easy to operate and does not require highly skilled operators. It also helps protect public health and ensures a reliable and safe water supply.
- The RO plant is very suitable for this area because several water-related and water-borne diseases are commonly reported. Providing safe and treated drinking water through an RO system can help reduce the incidence of these diseases.

RO Plant Model:

- Conclusion can show that RO Plant is very appropriate for this village and finally we decided to developed one mode which same protato type which will construct at village for purify water.
- This model is very effective and carried out many tests in the laboratory which understand that design of each unit is suitable according to their criteria and check result of output with we predicated and also find efficiency of model.

Following practical are performed in the laboratory:

1. MPN
 2. Total Dissolved solid
 3. Total Hardness
 4. PH
- These four test samples have collected from following points
 - Initial point – start point
 - Intermediate – after softening
 - Final point – after UV

Table.6. Comparison for Input & Output water

Sr. no	Description	Permissible Mg/l	Input Mg/l	Out put Mg/l	Efficiency in percentage
1	DISSOLVED SOLIDS	2000	7024	561	92.01 %
2	PH	6 to8	6.68	8	----
3	TOTAL HARDNESS	600	3144	140	76.66 %
4	CALCIUM (AS Ca) mg/l	200	661	133	69.74 %
5	MAGNESSIUM (AS Mg)	100	373	40	89.27 %
6	CHLORIDES (AS Cl) mg/l	1000	2148	540	74.86 %
7	SULPHATES (AS SO ₄)	400	524	110	79.00 %
8	NITRATES (AS NO ₃) mg/l	45	112.96	30	73.44 %
9	FLORIDES (AS F) mg/l	1.5	0.18	0.2	5%
10	ALKALINITY (AS CaCO ₃)	600	160	175	0.09%

Reference:

1. Bhattacharya, Amit, (2001); Osmosis and Reverse Osmosis: Regulator of Life; Science and Culture, January-February, 2001; pp 47-48
2. Byrraju Foundation report, 2006, Safe drinking water: An initiative in rural transformation by Byrraju Foundation CGWB, 1995,
3. Studies on conjunctive use of surface water and groundwater resources in Mahi-Kadana irrigation project, Gujarat.
4. Kumar, D., 2005, Rural Water Supply and Sanitation in Gujarat: sector assessment study, report submitted to WASMO, Government of Gujarat.
5. Dow Water & Process Solutions FILMTEC™ Reverse Osmosis Membranes, Technical Manual.
6. T.V. Arjunan, H.S. Aybar and N. Nedunchezian, (2009), 'Status of solar desalination in India', Renewable and sustainable Energy Reviews.
7. M.A.S Malik, G.N. Tiwari, A. Kumar, and M.S. Sodha, (1982) 'Solar Distillation', Pregamon Press, Oxford UK, pp.8–17.
8. C. Shen, Ya-Ling He, Ying-Wen Liu and Wen-Quan Tao, (2008), 'Modeling and simulation of solar radiation data processing with Simulink', Journal of Simulation Modeling Practice and Theory, 2, pp. 721-735.

9. K. Vinothkumar and R. Kasturibai (2008). 'Performance study on solar still with enhanced condensation'. Desalination, 230, 51–61.
10. Ground water and well water quality in alluvial aquifer of Saurashtra and Kutch in proceeding of IWMI-Tata water policy.
11. Coastal Area Development Programme "*Ensuring water security and promoting safe sanitation in the coastal Villages of Gujarat* assessment of groundwater hazards in coastal belt of Jamnagar district of Gujarat.
12. Ground water and well water quality in alluvial aquifer of Saurashtra and Kutch in proceeding of IWMI-Tata water policy.
13. Report of CGWB, "The Dynamic groundwater resources of India" published in 2004.
14. Total dissolved solids (TDS) in drinking water. WHO/SDE/WSH/03.04/16.
15. A Case for Pipelining Water Distribution in the Narmada Irrigation System in Gujarat, India, Tushaar Shah, Sunderrajan Krishnan, Pullabhotla Hemant, Shilp Verma, Ashish Chandra and Chillerege Sudhir IWMI WORKING PAPER 141

Books:

1. Water pollution, Author S.K Aggrawal Publication: APH Publication New Delhi published 2012
2. Water supply Engineering, Author S.K Garg, Standard Publishers Distributors
3. Irrigation and water supply, author A.K Arora, Standard Publishers Distributors

Govt. Published Literature:

1. Ground water scenario of India 2009-10, ministry of water resources
2. Planning Commission, 2002, India Assessment: Water supply and sanitation
3. Ground water recharge of coastal areas(2010)
4. Baseline survey on salinity in coastal areas of Jamnagar, Gujarat (2008)

Web sites:

1. www.planetkerala.org
2. www.engineering-resources.com
3. www. Frank water.org
4. www.ide-tech.com
5. www.pall.com